

WHOLODANCE

Whole-Body Interaction Learning for Dance Education

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Deliverable 2.1

Recruitment Protocol and informed consent form

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Sarah Whatley	First draft – collating examples for different forms	1.0	20/3/16
Karen Wood	Second draft - amendments	1.1	23/3/16
Sarah Whatley	Final draft – review	1.2	27/3/16
Rosa Cisneros	Final review and final draft	2.0	31/3/16

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Introduction

The success of the WhoLoDancE project is dependent on being able to build a repository of dance movements and to do this we need to draw on the expertise and experience of dancers who are competent practitioners in a range of dance genres. A number of dancers will be invited to perform set sequences of movement in a variety of dance genres for both video and 3D capture. Most dancers will be drawn from the project consortium. Any dancer who is not a member of the WhoLoDancE project team will receive a Participant Information Sheet and be required to sign an Informed Consent Form as a mandatory precondition for their involvement in the study. Both these documents will need to be approved by each participating research organisation's ethics committee before distributing to participants. Gaining ethical approval ensures that the project team is proceeding responsibly with due care for the participants and the storage of data that will be produced as part of the data capture process. Whilst it is not possible to anonymise the video recordings, these recordings will be made as part of the research process for internal visual reference, to assist in the database creation process and to define the shot-lists for the 3D motion captures so will not enter the public domain without prior permission being specifically sought from the participant. All video and 3D records will be retained securely and no personal data of the participants will be stored.

It is the duty of all researchers to ensure that any research activity meets the highest ethical standards. The project team has submitted the research protocol and associated documents for ethical review and clearance to Coventry University's research committee in line with its requirement that all subject related research obtain ethical approval before undertaking any research involving human participants. Ethical review and approval will also be sought from other participating research organisations as appropriate. WhoLoDancE falls under Coventry University's requirement that ethical approval is required for any research, design studies, artistic studies, experiments, survey work, questionnaires, interviews, focus groups or case studies.

Protocol for recruiting dancers

For each investigation activity, details on procedures and criteria used will be made readily available to the participants. The protocol for recruiting dancers will involve the following processes:

- Partners identify appropriate practitioners from within their own networks;
- Prior to video and 3D capture, dancers are provided with both documents and will be required to sign the Informed Consent Form, which will be countersigned by a member of the project team;
- When signatures are confirmed, the filming and captures can proceed.
- The form should be returned to Sarah Whatley, Coventry University, for storing and future reference.
- Dancers are able to withdraw from the study at any point; it will be made clear that participation is voluntary.

Participant Information Sheet

The Participant Information Sheet includes the following information:

- Outline of the project, its aims and experimental procedures
- Duration of the project
- The nature of the participation
- Risks and benefits of taking part
- What will happen to the participant's data.
- Key Contact details
- Withdrawal Options

Informed Consent Form

A sample Informed Consent document and an information sheet is included in this document. The Informed Consent Form includes a number of statements that the participant needs to tick in order to proceed. The

form is designed to be clear and straightforward, aimed at ensuring the participant understands and agrees to participation. The form requires no sensitive data to be collected (such as age, health, sexual orientation, ethnicity, political opinion, religious or philosophical conviction).

Both the Participant Information Sheet and the Informed Consent Form will be translated into French, Italian, Greek and other languages as and if required. The document shall be downloadable from the Project's website and a translated version will be readily available.

Ethics in Research

When performing experiments on humans, WhoLoDancE will also strictly observe, in every detail, the Charter of Fundamental Rights of the EU. In particular, it will guarantee the right to the integrity of persons (Article 1) and will conform with any detail in Article 2, respecting the free and informed consent of any person concerned in the experiments, avoiding any use of making the human body or its parts a source of financial gain, and being not concerned with eugenic practices and cloning.

Concerning the inclusion of human beings in experimental activities, WhoLoDancE will comply with relevant national and international regulations, and special attention will be paid to the observance of Article 5 of the Convention of the Council of Europe on Human Rights and Biomedicine, signed in Oviedo on 4 April 1997, regarding free consensus of healthy and disabled people (Article 17) in cases of experiments conducted with humans.

Finally, all data will be stored in secure and locked storage, or through encrypted computer files, to protect personal data and to comply with the relevant national and EC regulations regarding data protection. If an ethical issue arises, WhoLoDancE will act in accordance with Directive 95/46/EC of the European Parliament and the Council of 24 October 1995 concerning the processing of personal data and the free movement of such data. On principle, every effort will be made to preserve the privacy of the participants, which means that in general the dancer's identity will be kept confidential by default, unless they themselves wish to be identified and their involvement to be published.

Project Documents

Participant Information Sheet:

Participant Information Sheet

- Whole-Body Interaction Learning for Dance Education Project (WHOLODANCE)

Funder: European H2020-ICT-2015

Lead Institution: Lynkeus, Italy

Duration: 36 months

Partners: Lynkeus (IT), Athena RC (GR), Motek (NE), Polimi (IT), UniGe (IT), Peachnote GmbH (GE), COVUNI (UK), STOCOS (SP), K. Danse (FR), LCGW (GR)

Researcher responsible for this task: Professor Sarah Whatley

Contact details:

Professor Sarah Whatley

Professor of Dance and Director: Centre for Dance Research (C-DaRE)

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1. Information about the project/Purpose of the project

WhoLoDanceE is a three year (January 2016-December 2018) Research and Innovation Action, under the framework of ICT2015 of H2020 aiming at designing and developing whole body interaction tools to support dance learning. The consortium of WhoLoDanceE consists of a) Technical Partners, b) Four Dance Experts partners from different countries (UK, Spain, France and Greece) with a mixed profile of Dance Education institutions and choreographing companies, covering four different dance genres (ballet, contemporary, flamenco, and Greek folk).

The aim of the project is to create new technologies for capturing and analyzing dance movement to facilitate whole-body interaction learning experiences for a variety of dance genres. Working together we will develop a protocol for the creation and/or selection of dance sequences drawn from different dance genres for different teaching and learning modalities. Our initial work has involved designing a methodology for selecting the appropriate shots for motion capturing, to acquire kinetic material, which will provide a satisfying proof of concept for Learning scenarios of particular genres.

In order to build a rich repository of dance movements we want to work with a range of dancers experienced in different dance genres who we can video to collect data in order to be able to select the appropriate shots for motion capture. This is where we would like your help. You have been invited to participate because you are an experienced dancer in one or more dance genres and we want to draw on your expertise to ensure the validity of the repository. Participating in WhoLoDancE would mean one or more of the following:

- Attending studio-based sessions and performing a set number of dance sequences to be videoed by the project team;
- Allowing the project team to place markers on you and your movement being captured in 3D format;
- Repeating dance sequences multiple times for video and/or 3D capture.

2. Why have I been chosen?

You have been chosen as a dance practitioner with expertise in one of the dance genres that we wish to focus on in WhoLoDancE.

3. What do I have to do?

You will be asked to perform sequences of dance movement following instruction/guidance, both for video and 3D captures. Participation is entirely voluntary.

4. What are the risks associated with this project?

We will ensure that risks are mitigated by ensuring that you have sufficient time for warming-up, that you can take breaks when you need to and that all work will take place in a safe and suitable venue. We therefore will ensure that you have the right conditions in which to work but we cannot take responsibility for your physical well-being. Your personal data will not be stored.

5. What are the benefits of taking part?

You will have the opportunity to reflect on your work and be involved in influencing new technologies in the area of dance practice. You will have experience of working with experts in 3D capture technologies and be able to benefit from any technologies that emerge out of the project.

6. Withdrawal options

You can withdraw from the study and request your information be deleted at any time, without giving a reason, up to 28 days following the date of your final participation.

7. Data protection & confidentiality

No personal data will be stored. Audio and video recordings will only be used for analytical and research purposes and will not be shared publicly, online or by other means.

8. What if things go wrong? Who can I complain to?

If you wish to make a complaint at any stage, you should discuss this with Professor Whatley in the first instance. If you wish to further pursue your complaint, you should contact:

Prof Ian M Marshall
Deputy Vice-Chancellor (Academic)
Coventry University, Priory Street, Coventry CV1 5FB
Tel: +44(0)2476 79 5293 Fax: +44(0)2476 88 8030

9. What will happen with the results of the study?

The results of the study will be published online through the dedicated WhoLoDancE website and at relevant conferences and via academic publishing. If you have any concerns about this, they will be discussed under 8 above, prior to publication.

10. Who has reviewed this study?

The study has been reviewed and approved by the EU Commission. The study has also been reviewed and approved by the ethics committee at each participating research institution.

11. Further information/Key contact details

For further details please refer to the WhoLoDancE Project website at: <http://www.wholodance.eu/>.

Informed Consent Form:**Whole-Body Interaction Learning for Dance Education Project (WhoLoDance)**
Informed Consent Form

- Please tick**
1. I confirm that I have read and understood the participant information for the above study and have had the opportunity to ask questions.
 2. I understand that my participation is voluntary and that I am free to withdraw at anytime without giving a reason.
 3. I understand that my dance movements will be captured in 3D format and will be used to build a data repository that will be anonymously used in this research project.
 4. I understand that my dance movement will be video recorded as part of the process of determining the shot-list for 3D capture and these video recordings will be used exclusively for research purposes and will not be published online or used for any other publication purposes without my prior agreement.
 5. I understand that my personal data will not be stored and my comments will not be associated with my name under any circumstances.
 6. I agree to take part in the research project
 7. I do not agree to take part in the research project

Name of participant:

Signature of participant:

Date:

Countersigned (project partner) –

Name:

Signature:

Date:

All forms should be returned to:

Professor Sarah Whatley, Centre for Dance Research (C-DaRE), Coventry University, Priory Street, Coventry CV1 5FB, UK. Email: s.whatley@coventry.ac.uk.

Additional Information

Ethics approval process:

The screenshot displays the Coventry University ETHICS portal. At the top, the Coventry University logo and the word "ETHICS" are visible. Below this is a navigation bar with tabs for "My ETHICS", "My Projects", "Support", and "Help". The main content area is divided into several sections:

- Left Sidebar:** A "Projects" menu with options: "Authorise as", "My Projects", and "Create Project (New)".
- Top Left:** A graphic showing a globe and binary code.
- Top Middle:** A message: "You are using the New Project Creation Process. Complete the Form below and Click Next to advance through all sections. Your Project is being Saved as you Click Next".
- Top Right:** A message: "You may require a Reader for Available Documentation:" with links to "Get Adobe Acrobat Reader - Download free Adobe® Reader®" and "Get Word Viewer - View, print and".
- Center:** Project details for "Project [P42604] Whole-Body Interaction Learning for Dance Education Project (WhoLoDance)". Below the title are buttons for "Project Details", "Comments (0)", and "Approval Steps".